

Kinetics of Substitution of Anionic Malonato Complexes of Chromium(III) by Orthophosphoric Acid

N. R. ANIPINDI, V. M. RAO and V. ANANTA RAMAM*

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair-530 003

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The substitution of tris (malonato) chromate (III) and *cis*-diaquobis (malonato) chromate (III) anions by orthophosphoric acid was studied at room temperature. The reaction was found to proceed in two paths: H^+ dependent and H^+ independent. The following rate law has been suggested

$$\text{Rate} = \{k'[H_3O^+] + k''\} [\text{Complex}] [H_3PO_4]^2 [H_2\text{mal}]^{-1}$$

where the values of k' and k'' are $1.11 \times 10^{-2} M^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$ and $1.07 \times 10^{-3} \text{min}^{-1}$ for the bis complex and $1.38 \times 10^{-2} M^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$ and $1.56 \times 10^{-2} \text{min}^{-1}$ for the tris complex.

SEVERAL workers^{1,2,3} have reported the aquation of malonato complexes of chromium(III). Literature survey of these complexes shows that the data on substitution studies is scarce. As a part of programme of our work on the substitution of dicarboxylate complexes of chromium(III)^{4,5} we report in the present communication the results obtained in the study of substitution of tris(malonato)chromate(III) and *cis*-diaquobis(malonato)chromate(III) by orthophosphoric acid[@]. This study suggests that the substitution reaction proceeds with the replacement of the malonate groups by orthophosphoric acid.

Experimental

Materials: Potassium tris(malonato)chromate(III) was prepared by the method reported by Britton and Jarret⁶ and its purity confirmed by analysis (Calc. for $K_3[Cr(C_3H_2O_4)_3]$. $3H_2O:Cr$, 9.82%; malonate, 57.82%; Found: Cr, 9.76%, malonate 57.62%.)

Pure potassium *cis*-diaquobis (malonato) chromate(III) was prepared by the method described in literature¹. (Calc. for $K[Cr(C_3H_2O_4)_2(H_2O)_2]$. $3H_2O:Cr$, 13.50%; malonate, 52.97%. Found: Cr, 13.79%, malonate 52.59%.)

All the other chemicals used were of reagent grade. The water used was distilled water passed through a mixed bed cation-anion resin.

Chemical Analysis: Chromium as determined by oxidising chromium(III) with alkaline hydrogen peroxide and estimating the resulted chromium(VI) with a standard Fe^{2+} solution using BDAS as indicator. Malonate was estimated by the method of Olson and Behnke⁷ after decomposing the complex with sodium hydroxide and filtering off $Cr(OH)_3$ formed.

The rate of the reaction was followed spectrophotometrically at 570 nm and 566 nm for tris complex and the bis complex respectively by following the changes in absorbance of the reactants using a Unicam SP600 spectrophotometer. The kinetic runs were followed employing requisite quantities of metal complex, orthophosphoric acid and sodium nitrate (to maintain ionic strength).

Results and Discussion

The pseudo first order rate constant was evaluated graphically by plotting $\log(A_t - A_\infty)$ vs time where A_t and A_∞ represent the absorbance at time 't' and at infinite time respectively. The plots were found to be perfect straight lines upto 80% completion of the reaction and rate constants were evaluated from the slopes. The rate constants were found to be reproducible (with an average error of $\pm 5\%$). The rate of the reaction was followed as a function of the metal complex, phosphoric acid, added malonate and molarity of nitric acid. The rate of the reaction was also followed at different ionic strengths. The results are tabulated [Table I(a), I(b), I(c)&I(d)].

The rate has been found to be increasing with increasing molarity of phosphoric acid, nitric acid and ionic strength. It can be seen from the tables that the rate constants at different molarities of nitric acid are greater than the k_{obs} in the absence of nitric acid suggesting the acceleration of the rate of substitution by the presence of H^+ . Under the experimental conditions the contribution of H_3PO_4 to $[H^+]$ is negligible since it is a weak acid. A plot of k_{obs} vs molarity of nitric acid gave a straight line with a positive intercept on the rate axis indicating thereby that the reaction proceeds along two paths: acid dependent and acid independent—the slopes (k') and intercepts

@ The product formed from *trans*-diaquobis (malonato) chromate(III) and orthophosphoric acid gave the same product as that from the *cis*- $Cr(mal)_2(H_2O)_2^-$ and $Cr(mal)_3^-$. But, the rate of the reaction could not be followed as there is not much difference in molar extinction values for the reactant and product at any wavelength.

TABLE I (a)—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT WITH PHOSPHORIC ACID MOLARITY.

[Cr(mal)₂]²⁻ = 0.004 M Temperature = 31.0 ± 0.2°C
 [Cr(mal)₂]⁻ = 0.004 M Ionic Strength (μ) = 3.0

[H ₃ PO ₄] (M)	k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	
	[Cr(mal) ₂] ²⁻	[Cr(mal) ₂] ⁻
1.0	0.59	0.88
1.5	0.78	0.94
2.0	1.02	1.09
2.5	1.46	1.20
3.0	1.78	1.37
3.5	2.18	1.51
4.0	2.84	1.72

TABLE I (b)—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANTS WITH METAL COMPLEXES.

Temperature = 31.0 ± 0.2°C [H₃PO₄] = 3.0 M ; μ = 3.0

[Metal Complex] (M)	k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	
	Cr(mal) ₂ ²⁻	Cr(mal) ₂ ⁻
0.002	1.72	1.30
0.003	1.79	1.36
0.004	1.78	1.37
0.005	1.69	1.42
0.006	1.81	1.43
0.007	1.80	1.39

TABLE I (c)—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANTS WITH ADDED MALONATE.

[Cr(mal)₂]²⁻ = 0.004 M [Cr(mal)₂]⁻ = 0.004 M
 Temperature = 31.0 ± 0.2°C ; [H₃PO₄] = 3.0 M ; μ = 3.0

[Malonate] (M)	k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	
	Cr(mal) ₂ ²⁻	Cr(mal) ₂ ⁻
0.002	1.70	1.31
0.004	1.62	1.24
0.006	1.56	1.18
0.008	1.46	1.11

TABLE I (d)—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANTS WITH HYDROGEN ION*.

[Cr(mal)₂]²⁻ = 0.004 M [Cr(mal)₂]⁻ = 0.004 M
 Temperature = 31.0 ± 0.2°C [H₃PO₄] = 3.0 M ; μ = 3.0

[H ⁺]	k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	
	Cr(mal) ₂ ²⁻	Cr(mal) ₂ ⁻
0.25	1.97	1.37
0.50	2.25	1.68
0.75	2.60	1.87
1.00	2.93	2.18

* Source of Hydrogen ion : Nitric acid.

(k^r) of the plots representing the acid dependent and acid independent paths were calculated. The increase in rate constant with increasing ionic strength is in agreement with the change expected in a reaction between the ions of the same charge type. There is a decrease in the rate constant with an increase in the concentration of added malonate.

The absorption spectra of the products obtained from the substitution on the tris complex and the bis complex by H₃PO₄ are identical with two broad absorption peaks in the wavelength regions 430-450 nm and 610-640 nm. Ion exchange studies on the product species failed to show the presence of either cationic or anionic phosphato complexes. Hence the product species may be possibly neutral of the type Cr(H₂PO₄)(HPO₄)³⁻.

The following mechanisms are suggested to explain the experimental observations, assuming the formation of a conjugate acid in an equilibrium step.

Bis Complex

Acid dependent path :

Acid independent path :

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{Complex}][\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4]^2 [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+][\text{H}_2\text{mal}]^{-1} + k_2 K_3 K_4 [\text{Complex}][\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4]^2 [\text{H}_2\text{mal}]^{-1}$$

$$= \{k'[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+] + k''\} [\text{Complex}][\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4]^2 [\text{H}_2\text{mal}]^{-1}$$

where $k' = k_1 K_1 K_2$ and $k'' = k_2 K_3 K_4$.

Tris Complex

Acid dependent path :

Acid independent path :

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{Complex}][\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4]^2 [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+][\text{H}_2\text{mal}]^{-1} + k_2 K_3 K_4 [\text{Complex}][\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4]^2 [\text{H}_2\text{mal}]^{-1}$$

$$= \{k'[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+] + k''\} [\text{Complex}][\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4]^2 [\text{H}_2\text{mal}]^{-1}$$

where $k' = k_1 K_1 K_2$ and $k'' = k_2 K_3 K_4$.

The k_{obs} is greater for the bis complex than the corresponding values of the tris complex upto 2.0M H_3PO_4 , beyond which a reverse trend is observed. This may be due to the greater stability of the tris complex than the bis complex⁹. The reverse trend observed at higher molarities of H_3PO_4 may be due to predominance of the aquation process¹⁰.

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